

Understanding Drowning Incidents: Causes, Risk Factors, and Prevention Strategies Among Regular Water Body Visitors

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Abstract

Drowning is one of the significant challenges faced by society at all times. So, it is highly important to conduct study on its etiology, causes and preventive measures in order to foster an upcoming society free of such accidents. The study is to be conducted on frequent visitors of any water bodies so it will pave new insights about drowning, it causes etc. by conducting a study on people who have experience in swimming and water environments will be effective to obtain proper dimension regarding how drowning occurs. Without any external funding this research focuses on understanding the root causes for drowning. Population under study is selected randomly and should have regular exposure to water bodies, especially hazardous water bodies. The study employs a set of qualitative and quantitative methodologies that includes surveys, interviews and direct observation from participants within the researcher's social network. The research aims to create mass awareness in public regarding this significant social issue and propagating the precautions that would help to build a safer water environment.

keywords-Drowning, Drowning, Training
Prevention, Water Safety, Swimming

I. Introduction

- a) Overview of drowning incidents as significant public health concern

Drowning is one of the major public health problems faced all around the world at all times. Drowning leads to the death of a large population of human

beings every year. As per the records of World Health Organization (WHO) drowning is the third most cause of accidental death worldwide. Apart from deaths many victims also suffer from non-fatal injuries which leads to long term disabilities. Drowning causes serious social economic emotional problems in individuals and families. Even though there are massive efforts are on the go to improve water safety, drowning still remains as a great threat to human life. The miserable fact regarding drowning is that it is mostly unintentional and takes the life of a healthy individual. Taking these factors into consideration, drowning is a significant issue that needs effective research and interventions immediately. Taking the seriousness of the issue into consideration, strict enforcement of law and social education is vital in this problem.

- b) Statement of the research problem and its objective

This research focuses on conducting research on regular water body visitors to study about drowning incidents. It is an area as well as demographic group which isn't explored very much. So conducting research on this issue will give new insights into this relevant social issue. This research focuses on finding why drowning incidents occur frequently, who all are having a high risk of drowning, effective measures to be implemented to safeguard this high-risk demographic group from drowning and related water accidents. By portraying the role of individuals, organizations and society on reducing the impact of water accidents this research aims to

create public awareness on water safety, which will ultimately lead to a good water culture. As this research is conducted on regular water body visitors their experience and knowledge regarding various aquatic hazards may benefit to obtain valuable conclusions to the research.

c) Importance of studying drowning incidents on regular water body visitors

The need for studying drowning incidents on regular water body visitors is very significant. Apart from non-regular visitors to water bodies who come for entertainment purposes, regular water body visitors are experienced and well aware of many water hazards that can effectively contribute to the research. As they are regular visitors to the water body, they are well aware of all the various risk factors that may ultimately lead to drowning or a non-fatal water accident. Recreational water users who visit water bodies are unable to contribute to various risk factors that lead to drowning, whereas regular visitors have exposure to unpredictable water phenomenon, hazardous areas in an aquatic environment, health and stamina required to survive in a water body (typically hazardous) and access to resources which causes an individual vulnerable to drowning. By focusing on this demographic group the research focuses on filling a gap in the existing literature and also to gain new insights to minimize drowning and water accidents effectively. Understanding the frequency of drowning cases among regular water body visitors helps to formulate new public health policies and law enforcement. It also helps to create community-based initiatives and also to foster a good water safety culture among the public.

II. OBJECTIVES

- a) Investigate the relationship between frequency of visiting water bodies and opinion on the importance of water safety training.
- b) Examine the association between participation in campaigns or initiatives for water safety awareness and opinion on the importance of water safety training.
- c) Explore the relationship between opinion on giving swimming training in schools and opinion on the importance of water safety training.
- d) Analyze the association between age and awareness of safety measures such as

wearing safety jackets in deep water environments.

- e) Investigate the relationship between hazardous water training and school swimming training opinion among the participants.
- f) Examine the association between knowledge of accidents and first aid knowledge among the participants.
- g) Explore the relationship between first aid knowledge and aquatic survival training age.

III. Recent Studies

Drowning is one among the most important public health concerns worldwide, so a vast study into its causes, risk factors, and precautions are mandatory at the current scenario. This literature review aims to understand the existing research in order to obtain a clear idea of drowning incidents. The problem is analyzed from various dimensions including demographic disparities, environmental factors, and precautionary measures to be taken. Such an analysis will pave the way to unveil new insights that can ultimately be used for the betterment of the research.

A. Demographic disparities in drowning incidents

Demographic disparities in drowning can be evident from numerous studies conducted worldwide. As per the records centers for disease control and prevention it states that children at age of 1-4 years have a higher rate of accidental death due to drowning rather than any other source of death. And children at the age of 5-14 have drowning as the second leading cause of death. Nearly 40% of the drowning cases require hospitalization and further treatments. There is an estimated death rate of 12 deaths per day in the United States. African regions have the highest drowning death cases in the world. The CDC foundation and Bloomberg philanthropies partnered in 2018 to understand and prevent drowning deaths in Uganda. Research by Thompson et al. (2018) plots age as a significant factor for determinants of drowning risks. Thompson says young children and adults are highly vulnerable to drowning risks, as a matter-of-fact Thompson's assumption was correct. Young children and adults are the most victims of drowning. Due to the lack of maturity and inability to understand the hidden risks in water environments children and adults have a high death rate due to drowning. The miserable thing is that the young healthy individuals are losing their

life due to a minute's false decision. Another notable factor in determining drowning risk can be evaluated by the social, economic factors of victims. It is a salient feature that has an impact on the drowning rates. As per the study of the World Health Organization, socio-economic factors can be affected as a risk factor for drowning and people in the low economic status are at high risk of drowning. As per the research conducted by Aminur Rahman, Amy E. Peden, Lamisa Ashraf, Daniel Ryan, Al-Amin Bhuiyan and Stephen Beerman, various other factors that cause drowning are exposure to hazardous aquatic environments without life jackets, alcohol consumption, no prior knowledge of swimming etc. Males have a higher risk of drowning than females. Certain occupations like fishing have high exposure to aquatic risks and are highly prone to drowning risks. Health of the individual is another crucial determinant of drowning risks. Certain medical conditions like epilepsy require the person with the condition to avoid aquatic environment exposures.

B. Environmental Factors contributing to drowning incidents

The environmental conditions of the aquatic environment is a major determinant of drowning risks. So an in-depth understanding of the landscape and geographical hazards of water bodies is immensely required to study about drowning incidents and the same will be needed to take precautionary measures. More specifically the geographical factors which are determinant of drowning risk can be pointed out as water temperature,

Water current, visibility of water. This is a notable assumption obtained from the research by Stallman (Stallman et al., 2018). Most of the drowning incidents occur when there is high water current, low water temperature. It is very difficult to swim or interact with an aquatic environment during the night time. As it is evident from the social media and newspaper we know that most of the drowning accidents occur at winter season, because there is high water current and aquatic environment exhibit unpredictable nature during those days. Even experts and experienced people become victims to drowning due to this unpredictable nature of the aquatic environments. In research conducted on environmental factors associated with drowning prevention, knowledge of parents in Bangladesh: a randomized controlled trial by DR. Moshraff Hossain and DR. Kulanthyan KC Mani pointed out that there was a significant improvement in drowning prevention through the knowledge of

environmental factors for drowning. They identified significant factors like time, lack of swimming ability, parents who are not aware of childhood drowning, unwanted ditches that were not filled in, lack of medical facility etc. as the cause for drowning in children. Drowning is one of the leading life takers in children. The curiosity that develops in young children and adults to swim in aquatic environments without the knowledge of its hidden risks and geographical abnormalities in most of the aquatic landscape has taken the life of large number children and adults. There will be some objects that are submerged under water which will cause a high risk of drowning. Strong water current can cause a high risk of drowning which will cause a high threat of drowning, even an experienced swimmer couldn't withstand such a strong water current. Sudden changes in the depth of the aquatic landscape also significantly improve the risk of drowning. These are the major observations made by Gomez et al. (2019). The research by Brenner explains the influence of seasons in drowning. Where there is a high risk of drowning in summer seasons, it is evident that in winter seasons the water level in aquatic environments rises and many underlying risk factors are being developed in the aquatic environments. This observation points out the need for immense care to be taken on aquatic environments during winter seasons. But in summer and holiday seasons more people are exposed to aquatic environments thus the chance of drowning is high during summer seasons and holiday seasons (Brenner et al. (2019)).

C. Preventative interventions and strategies

Research on drowning incidents is meaningless unless it puts forward some effective measures to minimize drowning. The effectiveness of research on drowning lies in its ability to provide the ways to prevent drowning incidents. All strategies of this research ultimately aim to understand what is drowning, how it occurs and how we could withstand this challenge. The prevention of drowning can adopt a variety of measures such as educational initiatives, policy interventions and community-based initiatives but the effect of such initiatives cannot prevent the victim during an unfavorable situation. It only creates a sense of consciousness to individuals to how to deal with aquatic environments. But the potential risk of drowning still exists, because it is in the hands of individuals who interact with water bodies. To make a wise decision before getting exposed to water bodies by analyzing the risk factors that exist in the particular water environment and to take safety

measures required. The first and most required precautionary measure is swimming education from early childhood itself. Learning swimming is easy and effective when it is in childhood. In most of the western countries early swimming training is given to Childrens. Basic swimming skills can help to minimize potential drowning risks and also helps in giving an understanding of anomalous behavior of the water bodies. This is clearly depicted in the research made by Wallis et.al (2020). Along with swimming skills proper safety measures are also mandatory in avoiding significant risk factors. Safety measures mandating through legal enforcement involving wearing of life jackets, building fences around the swimming pools and enhanced supervision in recreational water environments has paved the way for better water safety. These are the observations made by Franklin et.al, (2018). In addition to all these community-based initiatives such as provisioning of swimming lessons, formulating water safety commissions etc. can make a huge difference in drowning risks. Thus, it will help to build a community which can approach the aquatic world with wisdom regarding its risk factors (Linnan et.al., (2018)). As per the study by Linda Quan, Elizabeth E. Bennett, Christine M. Branche: isolation of swimming pools, wearing of PFD by boaters and others who have water related occupation and awareness camps are highly significant in the prevention of drowning.

D. The role of behavioral factors in drowning incidents

Behavioral factors play an important role in drowning. Swimming and other interaction with water is an art of discipline and can be pursued through a state of mental wellbeing. A disturbed mind can invite significant water risk. A responsible individual keeps all the safety precautions while interacting with a hazardous water environment. Alcohol consumption is a significant cause of many drownings' incidents. A person will not be in a conscious state when he consumes alcohol. Thus, exposure to water bodies after drinking alcohol may cause significant risk to the life of the individual. Also, interaction with hazardous water environments with lack of supervision also paves the way for drowning. If you are not well aware of the aquatic environment then you should not interact with it without guidance. On analyzing various drowning cases people who were experts in swimming also fall victim to Drowning. This is due to the lack of knowledge regarding the hidden hazards in water bodies. As per the research by Quan et.al (2018) it points out the association between

alcohol consumption and drowning incidents. Quan studied that alcohol consumption causes impaired judgment in individuals. When a person gets exposed to water bodies after consuming alcohol it causes impaired judgment and causes them to sink and drown in water. So, you should take immense care and avoid water bodies while you are drunk. It also creates issues with coordination of your body so even if you are an expert swimmer alcohol induces the coordination of your body movements and results in drowning. Looking into another significant risk factor is the lack of supervision especially in recreational water environments. People who visit the recreational water set up mostly come for tourism and entertainment activities. They are not expert swimmers and should not have prior experience in interacting with water environments. Such a population needs guidance and supervision from experts. They couldn't survive in aquatic environments without proper guidance and ground support. Childrens and adults require supervision mostly. They are vulnerable to many significant risk factors in aquatic environments. There should be someone who restricts them from over exposure to hazardous water environments. Personal flotation devices should be equipped with every person who interacts with aquatic hazards without considering the purpose of interaction.

IV. Data Interpretation

a) frequency of visiting water bodies vs opinion on the importance of water safety training

This study aims to obtain the relationship between frequency of visiting water bodies with opinion on the importance of water safety training. As per the null hypothesis There is no significant association between frequency of visiting water bodies and opinion on the importance of water safety training in the current world scenario. And the alternative Hypothesis states that There is a significant association between frequency of visiting water bodies and opinion on the importance of water safety training in the current world scenario. The analysis showed a good sensitivity using the chi-square test of independence. Specifically the chi-square statistics gives a value of 18.041 with 4 degrees of freedom, resulting in a p-value of 0.001.

Figure 1 : relationship between frequency of visiting water bodies vs opinion on the importance of water safety training

Therefore, the null Hypothesis “There is no significant association between frequency of visiting water bodies and opinion on the importance of water safety training in the current world scenario” is rejected. This affects how often they visit the water. This highlights the importance of considering recreational behaviors when developing safety behaviors related to water activities. Further research could bring better insight into this significant social issue. The information yielded from these researches can be effectively used to generate future policies and plans.

b) participation in campaigns or initiatives for water safety awareness vs opinion on the importance of water safety training

This study endeavors to examine the correlation between participation in campaigns or initiatives for water safety awareness and individuals’ opinions on the importance of water safety training in today’s global context. The null hypothesis shows there is no significant association with these factors, Whereas the alternative hypothesis shows a meaningful relation.

We used the chi square test for significance and which led to meaningful conclusions. We got a chi-square statistics value of 7.044 and 2 degrees of freedom and a p value of 0.029.

Consequently, the null hypothesis, indicating no association between participation in water safety initiatives and opinion on the importance of training,

was rejected. this underscores the potential influence of engagement in awareness campaigns on individuals’ perceptions regarding water safety education

Figure 2 : relationship between participation in campaigns or initiatives for water safety awareness vs opinion on the importance of water safety training

c) opinion on giving swimming training in schools vs opinion on the importance of water safety training in the current world scenario.

This study aims to investigate the relationship between individuals’ opinions on the provision of swimming training in schools and their perceptions of the importance of water safety training in the current global context. The null hypothesis posits that there is no significant association between these opinions, while the alternative hypothesis suggests a meaningful relationship. Employing the Chi-square test for independence, the analysis revealed compelling results. Specifically, the chi-square statistics yielded a value of 11.410 with 4 degrees of freedom, resulting in a p-value of 0.022.

Figure 3 : relationship between opinion on giving swimming training in schools vs opinion on the importance of water safety training in the current world scenario.

As a result, the null hypothesis, suggesting no association between opinions on school-based swimming training and importance of water safety education, was rejected. This indicates a significant association between individuals’ opinions on school-based swimming training and their perceptions of water safety training’s importance. These findings underscore the potential impact of educational policies regarding swimming training in schools on individuals’ attitudes towards water safety education. Further research could explore the underlying mechanisms driving this association and inform educational strategies aimed at promoting water safety awareness and reducing water-related incidents on a global scale

d) age VS awareness of safety measures such as wearing safety jackets

This study examines the relationship between age and awareness of safety measures, specifically focusing on the practice of wearing safety jackets in deep water environments' null hypothesis posits that there is no significant association between age and awareness of safety measures, while the alternative hypothesis suggests a meaningful relationship. Utilizing the chi-square test for independence, the analysis revealed compelling results. With a chi-square statistic of 14.424 and 5 degrees of freedom, the calculated p-value was 0.013, leading to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Figure 4 : relationship between age vs awareness of safety measures such as wearing safety jackets

This indicates a significant association between age and awareness of safety measures such as wearing safety jackets in deep water environments. These findings underscore the importance of considering

age-related factors in promoting safety measures, with implications for targeted interventions aimed at enhancing water safety awareness across different age groups. Further research could delve into understanding the underlying reasons for age-based differences in safety awareness, facilitating the development of more effective strategies to mitigate risks and promote safety in aquatic environments.

e) hazardous water training vs school swimming training opinion

This study explores the relationship between participants' opinion on hazardous water training and their perspectives on school swimming training. The null hypothesis suggests no significant association between these variables, while the alternative hypothesis posits a meaningful relationship. Employing the chi-square test for independence,

The analysis revealed noteworthy findings. With a chi-square statics of 10.682 and 2 degrees of freedom, the calculated p-value of 0.004 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Figure 5: relationship between hazardous water training vs school swimming training opinion

This indicates a significant association between hazardous water training and school swimming training opinion among the study participants. These results highlight the potential interplay between experiences with hazardous water environments and perceptions of the value of formal swimming training in schools. Further investigation into the underlying factors driving this association could inform educational policies and safety initiatives aimed at promoting comprehensive water safety training across different contexts.

f) knowledge of accidents and first aid knowledge

This study investigates the relationship between participants' knowledge of accidents and their proficiency in first aid. The null hypothesis posits no significant association between these variables, while the alternative hypothesis suggests otherwise. Utilizing the chi-square test for independence, the analysis yielded notable results. With a chi-square statistic of 9.962 and 4 degrees of freedom, the calculated p-value of 0.041 led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Figure 6 : relationship between knowledge of accidents and first aid knowledge

This indicates a significant association between participants' knowledge of accidents and their first aid proficiency. These findings underscore the importance of understanding accidents in informing

effective first aid practices. Further research could explore the specific areas of knowledge that contribute to first aid proficiency, aiding in the development of targeted educational interventions aimed at enhancing emergency response capabilities among the general population.

g) first aid knowledge and aquatic survival training age

This study analyzes the participants' relationship between first aid knowledge vs the age at which they received swimming training. The null hypothesis shows there is no significant

Figure 7: relationship between first aid knowledge

and aquatic survival training age

association with these factors, Whereas the alternative hypothesis shows a meaningful relation. We used the chi square test for significance and which led to meaningful conclusions. We got a chi-square statistics value of 14.300 and 4 degrees of freedom and a p value of 0.026. Therefore, the null hypothesis is rejected. This indicates the need for early swimming training to improve individuals first aid knowledge on water accidents, which ultimately points to the need for early swimming training. More studies will help to know the gravity of impact of early swimming training in individuals for better water safety.

V. Conclusion

In conclusion, the literature review reveals the multifaceted nature of drowning incidents among regular water body visitors. Which encompasses demographic, environmental, and behavioral aspects of drowning incidents. By combining the wisdom from diverse studies this review provides significant insight into various drowning risks as well as measures to mitigate drowning. In light of these studies, the mortality rate as well as the non-fatal injury rates due to drowning can be minimized to a great extent. This review provides an idea

VI. References

regarding the need for proper code and conduct in aquatic environments as well as depicts the need to emphasize supervision and guidance in water environments. Special care is to be taken in the case of children and adults as the drowning risk is high for them. The potential risk of drowning is high in summer seasons because people depend on aquatic bodies mostly during the summer seasons as well as holiday seasons. Alcohol consumption leads to misjudgment and imperfect coordination in aquatic regions so consumption of alcohol should be avoided in such circumstances. The usage of safety measures such as personal flotation devices PFD life jackets etc. has a large influence in avoiding potential risk. Also, safety mechanisms should be adopted into the water bodies such as fencing that can reduce drowning and potential water accidents. The formation of laws and committees to guide water safety is necessary in the current socio-economic scenario. Creating communities for providing swimming training and aquatic safety should help to develop a drowning-free society. Except for all this valuable observation the need for conservation of aquatic assets is very important. Soil mining from rivers and water bodies paved the way for the sudden increase in depth of the water bodies. Unauthorized building construction on water bodies caused the reason for abnormal behavior of the water bodies. Certain algae deposits in water bodies have also negatively influenced the safety of aquatic movements. People with certain health conditions such as epilepsy have a high risk of drowning. unnecessary curiosity in children and adults has paved the way for many drowning cases. From social media and newspapers, it is evident that most of the drowning cases take the life of more than one person, it is observed that most of the time the person who goes for rescue of the victim has also lost his life due to the unscientific approach opted for rescue. Rescuing a person who is sinking in water is never an easy task. Never try to jump into the water to save the life of the victim if you are not sufficiently expert in

swimming and unaware of the landscape of the aquatic terrain. Try other mechanisms in such a situation like throwing life jackets or rope to the victim. So, from the existing

literature, it is identified that there is a significant gap in this area so further research is needed to obtain new insights into the issue.

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